

Processing of Korean monazite concentrate for the recovery of rare earth metals (REMs)

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Abstract : Rare earths metals (REMs) have gained immense awareness due to their inimitable properties and wide range of applications. REMs are naturally present in minerals like monazite, bastnasite, apatite, etc. The present work is focused on comparative study for the recovery of REMs from original Korean monazite and dephosphorized monazite by acid treatment. Direct leaching of original sample using dilute HCl at elevated temperature for 2 h maintaining pulp density < 100 g/L results in ~25% REMs dissolution, which increases to 45% by two-step leaching due to the presence of phosphate in the mineral which hinders the REMs leaching due to the formation of RE complex. However, >93% REMs is leached in single stage from dephosphorized monazite under same conditions. Systematic dephosphorization studies were made using pyro/hydrometallurgical methods. Further precipitation, solvent extraction or ion exchange method are used for the selective separation of REMs from the generated leach liquor.

Keywords : Rare earth metals (REMs), Korean monazite, dephosphorization, HCl.

Introduction

The popularity of rare earth metals (REMs) is escalating rapidly because they play imperative role as an industrial material with unique applications in various fields viz. fluorescent lamps, hybrid and electric cars, permanent magnets, superconductors, wind turbines, catalysts, etc.^{1,2}. The unsaturated 4f electronic structure of RE elements gives them unique properties to be used in luminescence, magnetism and electronics³. REMs are moderately available in hard rock and placer deposits of the earth's crust. They do not occur naturally as metallic elements but exists in a wide range of minerals of carbonates, oxides, phosphates, and silicates as trivalent cations. Some of these minerals with the approximate percentage of RE oxide content are shown in Table 1^{4,5}.

Among the best recognized rare earth minerals, only bastnasite, monazite and xenotime contain significant amounts of REMs along with other metallic constituents like titanium, thorium, zirconium etc.⁶. In most deposits, REs are such that they can be recovered as the primary product or as a co-products/by-products of certain other minerals. These RE minerals are located throughout the world, with usually large deposits occurring in few countries. Primarily, the production of REE has been found in China, Australia, India, Malaysia, Russia, etc. with China being the dominant world producer⁴. But recently, China, which controls 97% of world trade in REMs, has imposed restriction on its export. Consequently, the global demand of REMs is mounting and is expected to surpass the supply by 40,000 tonnes annually⁷. Hence, it is obliga-

Table 1. REE containing minerals with approximate percentage of RE oxide
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Carbonate		Phosphate		Silicate		Oxide	
Mineral	REO% (Approx)	Mineral	REO% (Approx)	Mineral	REO% (Approx)	Mineral	REO% (Approx)
Bastnasite	75	Apatite	19	Gadolinite	60	Fergusonite	53
Parisite	61	Monazite	65	Allanite	38	Loparite	30
Synchysite	51	Xenotime	61	Kainosite	38	Euxenite	24
Cebaite	32	Florencite	32	Britholite	32	Brannerite	9

tory to exploit indigenous resources and expand technologies to meet the future necessities of RE in various applications. Monazite, second most important source of RE is a phosphate mineral which generally contains about 70% oxides of REMs comprising of 20–30% Ce, 10–40% La and noteworthy quantity of Nd, Pr and Sm^{8,9}. In India, monazite is the main mineral in association with other heavy minerals, such as ilmenite, rutile, zircon, etc. The estimated reserve of monazite as explored by Department of Atomic Energy, India is 10.21 million tons (Mt) in 2005¹⁰. Some Indian companies are even engaged in mining and processing of beach sand minerals. But Korea is a representative poor resource country with limited reserve. So many studies have been made to develop REMs in Korea². Monazite mineral is chemically very stable and can be attacked by strong acid transforming the phosphate ion to di-hydrogen phosphate salt and phosphoric acid, leaving all the metal ions as water soluble salts. Thus, the phosphate matrix present in the mineral is destroyed in strong, hot acids and alkalis³. But typical approaches have been developed to recuperate the phosphate ion present in the mineral as a valuable product which is mainly used as fertilizer in the agricultural sector¹¹. Several researchers reported different processing technique for the recovery of REMs from monazite ore. Pressure leaching, electrogenerated chlorine leaching and concentrated sulphuric acid leaching were performed to investigate the leaching behavior of monazite concentrate with various temperature ranges². REMs recovery from a weathered-black-earth-slime consisting of Mn removal by reduction leaching with SO₂, ammonium chloride roasting, water leaching of roasted material and precipitation of RE as oxalate using oxalic acid is also investigated¹². Extraction of RE elements from monazite minerals is studied using fusion in NaOH¹³. Metallurgical processing of monazite have also been reported which include the Indian Rare Earth process where monazite are dissolved in 65–70% NaOH and the high temperature processing in which the mineral is treated at 980–1190 °C. In the chlorination process, monazite is mixed with charcoal and heated at 900 °C^{2,14}. Present paper describes the comparative study of acid leaching behavior of original Korean monazite and the dephosphorized monazite.

Various process parameters were studied and optimized for acid leaching. Thermal decomposition of Korean monazite to remove phosphate as a valuable product using soda roasting followed by water leaching is also discussed. The formation of sodium phosphate which can be used in the fertilizer industry is also described.

Experimental

Material :

The raw material used for experimental purpose is Korean monazite constituting ~30% other minerals viz. siliminite, iluminite and ziron (Fig. 1) which is also confirmed by the mineralogical analysis using zoom stereo microscope (Fig. 2). The chemical composition of the Korean monazite concentrate was found to contain ~50% rare earth oxides and ~30% phosphate as P₂O₅ as shown in Fig. 3. The X-ray diffraction spectra indicated the presence of rare earth phosphates like LaPO₄, CePO₄, NdPO₄, etc. and P₂O₅ as main peaks (Fig. 4). Particle size analysis of the original sample found <50% below 200 mesh and the average particle size was 150 mesh as presented in Table 2. This monazite concentrate was used for further processing studies without any further reduction as fine size effect the RE recovery. The chemical reagents used were of Merck products. Distilled water was used for preparing aqueous sample/solutions.

Method :

Leaching studies were carried out with diluted hydrochloric acid in 100 mL pyrex reactor fitted with a reflux

Fig. 1. Percentage of different minerals present in Korean monazite.

- ◆ Monazite (Yellow colour particles)
- ◆ Zircon (Yellow colour with strong luster than monazite)
- ◆ Silliminite (White in colour with elongated shape)
- ◇ Ilmenite (Black colour particles)

Fig. 2. Mineralogical characterization of Korean monazite.

Fig. 3. Chemical composition of the Korean monazite concentrate.

Table 2. Screen analysis of the monazite sample

Mesh size	Weight (fraction) (g)
+48	0.06
-48 + 65	0.23
-65 + 100	3.22
-100 + 150	20.37
-150 + 200	15.16
-200 + 250	6.33
-250 + 325	3.60
-325 + Pan	0.94

condenser, on a magnetic hot plate stirrer at an elevated temperature for 2 h maintaining solid to liquid ratio > 100 g/L. During dephosphorization experiments, monazite concentrate were homogeneously mixed with an alkali at different experimental conditions and roasted in a muffle furnace for phosphate decomposition. The roasted mass containing rare earth hydroxides (REHs) and sodium phosphate was mixed in hot distilled water in order to dissolve the phosphate ion. After dissolution, the mixture was filtered and the REHs left were dried which converts the hydroxides to oxides. Satisfactory mass balance was obtained for each set of the experiment. These left REHs were then again leached in diluted acids for REMs dissolution in the same manner as described above showing varying results. The content of phosphorous and other REMs were determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP-OES) [VISTA-PMX, CCD Simultaneous; Make Australia].

Results and discussion

Leaching studies :

To recover REMs from Korean monazite material, a hydrometallurgical process of acid leaching has been considered suitable. Sulfuric acid and hydrochloric acid were used as leaching media and were of reagent grade. Monazite possesses high chemical and thermal stability and is therefore, very difficult to dissolve in acid, merely by proton attack. Therefore, a suitable ligand is required to form complexes with the REMs. During concentrated H_2SO_4 digestion step, the sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) ion of H_2SO_4 acts as a ligand as follows :

But it results in loss of phosphate as H_3PO_4 . Hence, HCl is considered more suitable among the two acidic solutions.

Two step leaching of original Korean monazite :

The original Korean monazite sample containing oxides of RE and phosphate is put to HCl leaching and various process parameters were studied. It was found that the dissolution rate of REMs increases with increase

Fig. 4. XRD of the head sample of Korean monazite.

in acid concentration, temperature and time but only up to certain stage after which it either reaches to the equilibrium stage or shows very negligible leaching. Using diluted HCl at moderate temperature for 2 h and solid to liquid ratio < 100 g/L, only ~25% REMs dissolution (Fig. 5) takes place. The leach liquor and the chlorides of

Fig. 5. Percentage dissolution of REMs from original monazite after double acid leaching.

Fig. 6. Effect of roasting temperature on recovery of phosphate present in Korean monazite.

RE formed is separated as :

This study results in very small amount of phosphate dissolution. Thus, the RECl_3 obtained in first leaching process was again leached under the same experimental condition using diluted HCl which shows up to ~45% REMs

Fig. 7. Leaching of REMs from REO concentrate left after phosphate removal.

dissolution. This two-step leaching process is not successfully achieved because the presence of phosphate hinders the reaction from going forward as it causes pulverization due to the formation of RE complexes.

Single step leaching of dephosphorized Korean monazite :

Since the reaction between phosphorus and RE present in monazite results in the formation of various RE complexes, dephosphorization is essential for effective recovery of REM. Roasting experiments were performed to remove/recover phosphorous as a valuable product. Subsequently, the recovery of REMs from the REHs left after phosphate removal was carried out using acid leaching process.

Initially, monazite and NaOH are homogeneously mixed in a platinum crucible and kept in a muffle furnace for roasting at different temperatures. Different process parameters for roasting were studied. The fine particles of monazite sample were reduced to $RE(OH)_3$ on roasting with NaOH. Dephosphorization rate was found to increase with increase in NaOH concentration, roasting temperature and roasting time. The results presented in Fig. 6 show that 95% of the phosphates present was re-

Fig. 8. Process flow-sheet for the recovery of REMs from monazite concentrate.

moved using 1 : 1 weight ratio of sample and NaOH at 350 °C for 2 h. The reason behind decomposition of phosphate at 350 °C might be the melting point of NaOH which is 351 °C. After roasting for a given time, the samples were taken out and cooled down to room temperature followed by hot water dissolution in order to dissolve the phosphate present as water soluble sodium phosphate. The leach liquor was then filtered and the content of phosphorous was determined. The sample obtained was rich in REMs and was further put to the acid leaching process for its recovery. After analyzing various process parameters, an optimum condition is reached using diluted HCl at elevated temperature for 2 h which results in >93% REMs recovery from the dephosphorized monazite concentrate maintaining pulp density > 100 g/L as shown in Fig. 7. The leach liquor generated during these experiments is further put to solvent extraction or ion exchange methods for the selective separation of individual REMs.

Preparation of sodium phosphate salt :

The solution left after dissolving the roasted mass contains the phosphate ions in form of dissolved sodium phosphate which is put to evaporation process to prepare the salt. This salt of phosphate is an important fertilizer and is majorly used in the agricultural sector. Moreover, they are also very vital constituents in animal feed stocks, food and other chemical industries. The proposed process flow-sheet for the recovery of valuable phosphoric acid and rare earth metals is presented in Fig. 8.

Conclusion

From the above studies, it has been concluded that the effect of acid dissolution on original Korean monazite results in only ~45% REMs as RECl_3 and 25% phosphate recovery as H_3PO_4 by two step leaching process. However, the dephosphorization of Korean monazite by soda roasting results in >95% of phosphate recovery as sodium phosphate by water washing. The single step acid leaching of the water washed roasted mass resulted in

>93% REMs recovery. The leach liquor generated can be further used for the selective extraction of metals by solvent extraction or ion exchange method.

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References

1. E. Kim and K. Osseo-Asare, *Hydrometallurgy*, 2012, **113**, 67.
2. H. Shin, H. Park and K. Yoo, *Geosystem Engineering*, 2012, **15**, 118.
3. Y. Jiang, A. Shibayama, K. Liu and T. Fujita, *Hydrometallurgy*, 2005, **76**, 1.
4. J. B. Hedrick, U.S. Geological Survey, 983 National Center, Reston, VA 20192, 2004, Indiana.
5. www.bgs.ac.uk/downloads/start.cfm?id=1638.
6. J. C. B. S. Amaral and C. A. Morais, *Minerals Engineering*, 2010, **23**, 498.
7. Reuters, 2009. As hybrid cars gobble rare metals, shortage looms available at <http://www.reuters.com/article/2009/08/31/us-mining-toyota/USTRE57U02B200908312009>.
8. R. Thompson, "Speciality Inorganic Chemicals", University of Salford, 1980, Vol. 40, pp. 403-443.
9. C. K. Gupta and N. Krishnamurthy, "Extractive Metallurgy of Rare Earths", CRC Press, Florida, 2005. Print ISBN : 978-0-415-33340-5. eBook ISBN: 978-0-203-41302-9. DOI : 10.1201/9780203413029.fmatt.
10. <http://www.c-tempo.org/studies/AnOverviewofRareEarthElements.pdf>.
11. A. Z. M. Abouzeid, *Int. J. Miner. Process.*, 2008, **85**, 59.
12. R. Chi, G. Zhu, Z. Zhou and Z. Xu, *Metall. and Mater. Trans. (B)*, 2000, **31B**, 191.
13. <http://archivos.labcontrol.cl/wcce8/offline/techsched/manuscripts/un4d59.pdf>.
14. M. Lee and H. Jeon, *J. Kor. Inst. Res. Rec.*, 2010, **19**, 27.